

TOWARDS SWCNT-BASED HIGH PERFORMANCE MATERIALS: THE CASE OF EPOXY AND PEEK

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SUMMARY

The principal objective of this work is to demonstrate that the properties of a multi-ply carbon fiber structure of a practical size and interest can be enhanced significantly with the integration of SWCNT. This approach includes different stages from synthesis, purification, characterization, chemistry, to composite integration and evaluation.

Keywords: Polymer wrapped SWCNT, SWCNT functionalization, Integration, Epoxy, PEEK, reduced SWCNT

INTRODUCTION

Single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) exhibit the best mechanical, thermal and electrical properties of any known material. Coupled with their very large aspect ratios, SWCNT are the ultimate enhancer of composite properties. Unfortunately, despite the wide availability of SWCNT and despite many attempts, SWCNT-based composites have shown poorer performance than predicted.[1] The main reasons for this are the highly variable purity and quality of the SWCNT samples used, poor dispersion/exfoliation and poor interface compatibility with the matrix.

In a joint project between the National Research Councils of Spain (CSIC) and Canada (NRC) and McGill University, we have been working to solve these issues with respect to epoxy (thermoset) and polyetheretherketone (PEEK) (thermoplastic) matrices to allow fabrication of multifunctional materials based on SWCNT. This work focuses on different steps from SWCNT synthesis and purification as well as different approaches for their integration into the matrix of interest to their effects on the ultimate properties of the matrices.

To take full advantage of SWCNT in composite applications it is paramount to overcome SWCNT bundling force in order to uniformly disperse them as well as

increase the interaction with the matrix. Both of these goals can be reached through proper chemical modification of the SWCNT. This can be accomplished in a number of ways, including wrapping the SWCNT with a polymer chain or direct covalent functionalization to carbon atoms in the nanotubes. Regarding the covalent approach several strategies have been developed. One favourable method is to perform chemical reactions on reduced (negatively charged) SWCNT because the nanotube bundles are naturally exfoliated due to the negative charge repulsion and counter ion intercalation, and the reaction time is substantially reduced.[2]

Amine functional groups are highly versatile assets in different nanoscience and nanotechnology applications.[3-6] Starting with an acid treatment as the first step for the covalent grafting, amine functionality can be attached through carboxylic groups as linking points. In the nanocomposites field, particularly in epoxy resin composite preparation, this kind of functionalization holds high potential since these amine groups can initiate and propagate the crosslinking process with the epoxide groups. The presence of amine in a composite's reinforcement may cause its participation in the curing process leading to better anchoring into the epoxy matrix and thus positively affecting their properties, as suggested by other authors. [7]

Among the large variety of methods to integrate SWCNT into polymeric matrices, some kind of physical blending or non covalent functionalization is often preferred in order to preserve physical properties, such as electrical conductivity, very much related to the electronic structure of SWCNT.[8] Block copolymers are among the most efficient steric stabilizers for SWCNT. They interact with CNTs via weak Van der Waals forces, resulting in polymer wrapped, adsorbed or extreme-connected nanotubes.[9] This causes steric repulsions between polymer layers which, due to the entropy alteration, lead to a separation of tubes, making them easier to integrate into polymeric matrices. Choosing a block copolymer with one of the blocks chemically compatible with the target matrix, the other block compatible with SCWNT, and codispersing them in the target block copolymer, provides a way to prepare SWCNT-Polymer nanocomposites with a good dispersion. The role of the solvent is crucial when preparing liquid dispersions of wrapped SWCNT, which could selectively dissolve the blocks. If it is chosen properly, it may affect the surface interactions in a very specific way.

SYNTHESIS AND PURIFICATION OF SWCNT

High quality SWCNT can be synthesized reliably at the laboratory scale using the laser vaporization technique and arc discharge method. Arc discharge SWCNT were produced using Nickel and Yttrium as catalysts, following a procedure proposed elsewhere.[10] The atomic ratio was 2:0.5 or 4:1 (Ni:Y) and the production experiment was run under 660 mb of Helium, and an electrical output of 100 A / 20V. The laser system is a unique two-laser vaporization process developed at the NRC.[11] The process uses a high-energy pulsed Nd:YAG laser at 1064 nm to vaporize a solid target pellet positioned in the centre of a 1200°C furnace.

All currently known SWCNT synthesis techniques produce significant quantities of impurities, such as amorphous and graphitic forms of carbon and carbon encapsulated catalytic metal nanoparticles. Different purification processes, based on nitric acid

treatments and centrifugation,[12,13] were performed on 4:1 and 2:0.5 arc grown-SWCNT samples. The yields of carboxylated groups were determined by sodium ICPS of the carboxylic sodium salt. Purity evaluation was determined by optical absorption spectroscopy in the NIR region, following an experimental proposal by Itkis et. al.[14] Depending on the feedstock, after the purification processes, NIR purities were obtained in the range of 24 – 60%. Residual catalyst particles were determined, using ICPS technique to separately obtain Ni and Y wt%. Total oxygen content, which gives information about the degree of oxidation, was registered in a Carlo Erba 1108 Elemental Analyzer (Table 1).

Table 1. Elemental data on some arc discharge SWCNT sample before and after purification

SAMPLE	%NI	%Y	%O
As-grown arc SWCNT (2:0.5)	9.10	3.55	1.52
As-grown arc SWCNT (4:1)	17.5	2.6	1.7
Purified 2:0.5	4.03	0.98	17.08
Purified 4:1	0.33	0.22	30.4

SWCNT samples synthesized by laser and arc discharge methods were also purified using an in-house method (WCPP) based on successive steps of flotation and centrifugation that does not introduce a significant amount of defects to the SWCNT wall. As-produced and purified SWCNT synthesized by both methods were characterized using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), transmission and scanning electron microscopy (TEM, SEM), Raman spectroscopy and NIR optical absorption spectroscopy. The results are shown in table 2.

Table 2. Characterization of as-grown and purified (WCPP) laser and arc-grown SWCNT

SAMPLE	G/D RATIO¹	RESIDUAL MASS² (WT %)	RELATIVE PURITY (AA(S)/AA(T))³
As-grown arc-SWCNT	15.8	23.9	0.037
Arc-SWCNT purified	32.8	21.9	0.084
As-grown laser-SWCNT	15.2	12.5	0.037
Laser-SWCNT purified	34.5	7.9	0.110

¹From Raman Spectroscopy

²From TGA. In air at 900 °C.

³ Obtained by NIR optical absorption spectroscopy.[14]

CHEMISTRY AND INTEGRATION INTO MATRICES

Functionalized SWCNT have the potential for the development of high performance composite materials. Covalent and non covalent approaches have been pursued for the modification of SWCNT to solve the problems associated with bundling and the lack of interfacial interaction with the matrices of interest.

Integration of SWCNT into an epoxy matrix

A commercial trifunctional resin used in the aerospace industry, triglycidyl p-amino phenol (TGAP), with the trade name of Araldite MY 0510, was used as the polymeric matrix precursor. Aradur HT 976, 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulfone (DDS), was chosen as the curing agent.

We have worked extensively in the covalent chemistry on reduced SWCNT to incorporate different functionalities [2]. Negatively charged SWCNT are exfoliated as a result of electrostatic repulsion and have higher nucleophilic character than neutral SWCNT, exhibiting higher reactivity towards various reagents. They can react with the epoxide groups of the resin creating a direct connection to the resin backbone as represented in figure 1.

Figure 1. Reduction of SWCNT and its reaction with epoxide groups

The reduced SWCNT were incorporated in the epoxy monomer by a solution processing method. A stable suspension of reduced SWCNT in THF was mixed under nitrogen with the epoxy monomer by energetic shaking, bath sonication and finally using a high-shear mixer. The curing agent was then added after complete removal of the solvent. Although reduced SWCNT were homogeneously dispersed in the epoxy monomer, when the curing agent (DDS) was incorporated into the mixture and the curing cycle was started, the SWCNT tended to re-agglomerate at temperatures around 100 °C. Figure 2 shows optical images of the uncured mixture before and after the curing cycle had started. Hence, the curing process was examined in detail and the protocol was optimized to maintain the dispersion. This required the samples to be mechanically stirred until the viscosity becomes high enough to prevent segregation and re-agglomeration of the filler. At that point the composite was poured into the corresponding mould. SEM images of the cured composite showed an improvement in the dispersion quality (figure 3). These composites will be subjected to a wide range of mechanical, electrical and thermal tests to assess their potential performance as multifunctional structures.

Figure 2. Optical images of the SWNT/ MY0510/DDS system at 27 and 200 °C.

Figure 3. SEM image of composite films containing purified laser-grown SWCNT directly anchored to the epoxy resin.

Effective amine grafting to SWCNT was achieved following established protocols, starting from nitric acid treated SWCNT (arc discharge, 2:0.5) as previously mentioned. The acid functionalized SWCNT were suspended in N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) and treated with refluxing thionyl chloride.[5,13] The resulting acylated SWCNT were subsequently treated with a monoprotected alkyl diamine (N-Boc-1,6-diaminehexane) in DMF for 96h in argon atmosphere at 90°C.[5] The removal of the protective group was performed according to the literature,[15] and aminated SWCNT were obtained with a free amine content of 0.6-0.7 mmol/g SWCNT as determined by the Kaiser Test.[16] This amine content is in good agreement with the previous carboxylic determination and it points to a complete reaction of all the carboxylic groups present in the purified SWCNT. Infrared spectra of these aminated SWCNT can be seen in Figure 4. The successful removal of the protective group is evidenced by the disappearance of its characteristic bands; particularly the disappearance of the band at $\sim 1390\text{ cm}^{-1}$, typical doublet from a t-butyl group, is the ultimate proof. The remaining bands of the

unprotected product show the typical profile from amide and aliphatic functionalities, in good agreement with expected.

Figure 4. FTIR spectra for the Boc-aminated and unprotected SWCNT

The integration of these aminated SWCNT in the epoxy matrix was carried out by a solvent-free procedure. [17] DSC studies of the epoxy blends are currently in progress. As a preliminary result, enthalpy values of the epoxy-SWCNT with and without the curing agent seem to reveal a catalytic effect of the grafted amine groups on the curing process, but being unable to cause full curing at regular loadings.

Regarding the non-covalent approach, the SWCNT were dispersed in Pluronic® block copolymer and integrated in the epoxy resin, without participation of solvent during the integration.[17] The dispersion was prepared by adding 25mL of a Pluronic F68 aqueous solution (20 g/L) to 100 mg of acid treated arc-grown SWCNTs 2:0.5. Ultrasonication, with a Hielscher DRH-UP400S ultrasonic tip (400 W maximum power; 24 kHz maximum frequency), was applied for 60 min at 50% oscillation amplitude and 50% cycle time. The resulting dispersion was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for a duration of 35 min and the supernatant solution was decanted from the sediment. The supernatant was sonicated again for 4 hours under identical conditions. The sonicated supernatant was finally filtered at room temperature under vacuum, using polycarbonate filters (3 μ m pore size). In order to homogenize the particle size, the resulting solid (Pluronic wrapped SWCNT) was milled in an agate mortar, and then integrated into the epoxy matrix. TEM images, XRD and Raman data evidenced the debundling and proper wrapping of the SWCNT.[17]

The integration of these wrapped SWCNT into the epoxy matrix was carried out by a solvent-free procedure to avoid known drawbacks related to the use of solvents.[18] The process consists of two steps:[17]

- A premixing stage, where the wrapped SWCNT were successfully integrated into the epoxy precursor, until a completely homogeneous dispersion (with no visible aggregates) is achieved. Use of hot stirring and sonication.
- A mixing stage, where the epoxy monomer + wrapped SWNTs are blended with the curing agent by means of hot stirring, in optimized mixing time and temperature.[17]

Characterization of PEEK/SWCNT nanocomposites

The morphology, thermal and dynamic mechanical properties of PEEK/SWCNT nanocomposites, at 0.1, 0.5 and 1wt% SWCNT content, were also extensively investigated. An efficient dispersion of the CNTs inside the matrix was achieved by a combination of ball milling and mechanical treatments in ethanol media, as revealed by SEM micrographs of fractured film surfaces.

Crystallization and melting experiments indicate a slight decrease of the crystallization temperature with increasing SWCNT content, whereas the fusion peak temperature remains almost constant, as it can be observed in Figure 5. This behaviour can be explained by a nanoconfinement effect [19], which slows down the crystallization process and leads to lower crystallization temperatures for the nanocomposites. Small differences were found in the level of crystallinity of the different samples, as calculated from X-Ray diffraction and DSC measurements. Composites containing less than 0.5wt% SWCNT exhibited a higher degree of crystallinity and crystallite size than the neat matrix. At higher concentrations, the tube network restricts the polymer chain diffusion and hinders the formation of large-size crystals.

Figure 5. Non-isothermal DSC scans of PEEK/laser grown SWCNT (LC1m) nanocomposites at rates of 10°C/min, for samples with different SWCNT contents. Left: Crystallization thermograms; Right: Heating thermograms.

TGA thermograms revealed a substantial increase in the initial and maximum rate degradation temperatures under dry air and nitrogen atmospheres with increasing CNT loading. Similar thermal stability was found for composites prepared with purified arc-grown and laser-grown SWCNTs.

Figure 6. Left: Temperature dependence of the storage modulus E' and loss modulus E'' of PEEK/LC1m nanocomposites, for different SWCNT contents, obtained from DMA measurements at frequency of 1Hz. Right: Storage moduli difference between the nanocomposites and the pure PEEK as a function of temperature.

DMA spectra shown in Figure 6 reveal that the storage modulus increases, while loss modulus decreases, with increasing SWCNT content. The rate of change of the moduli is higher at extremely low concentrations, and gets progressively slower as the nanotube loading rises. This phenomenon can be attributed to weaker interfacial interactions between the tubes surfaces and polymer matrix chains happening when a larger concentration regime is reached [20]. SWCNT restrict molecular mobility and consequently increase slightly the glass transition temperatures. The largest shift is found among composites with more homogeneous and fine distribution of the SWCNTs, that also exhibit enhanced rigidity, in particular those incorporating laser grown SWCNT, probably due to the improved quality and properties of this type of filler.

CONCLUSION

SWCNT synthesized by the laser vaporization technique and arc discharge method have been successfully incorporated into both thermoset and thermoplastic matrices. Different covalent and non-covalent functionalization strategies were explored in order to improve SWCNT dispersion and interaction with a trifunctional epoxy system. The addition of curing agents affect the quality dispersion and a mixing protocol need to be developed. Significant improvements in PEEK storage modulus and glass transition temperature have been achieved by incorporating as-grown laser SWCNT and arc-grown acid purified SWCNT as reinforcement. The highest improvement is observed in composites incorporating as grown laser-SWCNT, probably due to their higher crystallinity and fewer side-wall defects.

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